

Stakeholders Recovery Strategy of Bali Tourism Sector in the Post-Pandemic New Normal Era

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ABSTRACT: This investigation was driven in Bali Tourism Destination and organized using a relative and corroborative examination study. The exploration instrument is taken from the public authority report which manages wellbeing convention for the travel industry area and afterward contrasted and the fact of the Bali Tourism Destination. The pointer utilized in this examination is the application (CHSE) Clean, Health, Safety, and Environment in the business' convenience, eatery, and vacation spot, and furthermore clarifies wellbeing conventions that apply to the travel industry ventures in Bali Tourism Destination. E-tourism has a critical occupation as a platform between the movement business creators and likely tourists. It made in Indonesia as of now has not tended to the main piece of giving information and sureness to tourists when they choose to visit a travel industry objective. The objections, lodgings, and all related areas should manage the execution of The Indicator of Clean, Health, Safety, Environment (CHSE) principles on their business activities. This investigation utilizes just a work area research strategy with information and data search methods on the web, auxiliary sources, and different wellsprings of logical distributions.

KEYWORDS: Business Operations, Clean, Environment, Health, Safety

INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 outbreak was firstly reported to have happened in Wuhan province China and it soon spread over other regions including Bali in Indonesia. Many people were worried that the outbreak could severely affect Bali since it is a famous tourist destination. Nevertheless, in the mid of May 2020, the causality reported four people died due to the virus; two of them are foreigners. Affecting life, the rise of the COVID-19 outbreak has disappointed many people that so many sporting events, festivals, and other gatherings were canceled due to fears of transmission through humans to other humans; and this happens all over the world. Educational institutions and tourism facilities, like hotels, restaurants, and tourist objects were closed temporarily; and the teaching-learning process is performed online. Disappointed, upset, and other dissatisfaction can be understood as perhaps activity has been planned a long time ago, but the safety of all is of the utmost importance that efforts should be attempted by all (Xu, et al. 2020).

The impact of the Covid-19 outbreak pushed the government to officially appeal to the public to reduce activities outside the home to stop the spread of the COVID-19 coronavirus in Indonesia. Utilizing technology, work may be electronically done from home. The appeal is intended for the community so that activities such as study, work, worship, and other activities involve many people. After all, quarantine is one of the ways the government does to stop the spread of infectious diseases despite the fact the success depends on the disciple of the person and the surroundings. Quarantine is generally carried out on people or groups who have no symptoms but are affected by the disease. It keeps them away from others so they do not infect anyone. It is not the only way to protect ourselves during an outbreak such as the COVID-19 coronavirus (Olivia, et al., 2020; Utama, et al., 2020).

Bali still leads the tourism sector as the best in the economic development sector. Look into before the Covid-19 outbreak, at the role of tourism in its contribution to Bali's GRDP, there is a noticeable increase. Bali's regional economic development, through the three sectoral strategies, is continuously being developed, which in turn can increase the economic growth of the Bali region, until 1996 the economic growth reached 8.16% above the national economic growth of 7.82% (Utama, et al., 2020).

At the time of this economic crisis in 1997, the economic growth of the Bali region was still 5.81% and the national economic growth at that time was 4.70%. At the height of the economic crisis in 1998, the regional economy of Bali contracted -4.04%, while the contraction at the national level reached 13.20%. After the implementation of the policy, the performance of Bali's

economic structure in 2020 showed an imbalance where the primary sector was only 14.50%, the secondary sector 18.80%, and the tertiary sector 69.71%. There has been a new imbalance; wherein 1971 the primary sector was 67.90%, secondary 8.34%, and tertiary 23.76%. In 2020 became the primary sector 14.50%, the secondary sector 18.80%, and the tertiary sector 69.71% (Utama et al., 2020; 2021).

Table 1. Development of Bali's Economic Structure 1970-2020

Years	Distribution of Sectors		
	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
1970	54.64%	2.76%	40.60%
1980	50.58%	9.81%	39.70%
1990	34.96%	11.39%	53.64%
2000	19.98%	13.93%	66.09%
2010	18.67%	16.73%	64.60%
2020	14.50%	18.80%	69.71%

Source: Bali Province in Number (2020) (Utama, et al., 2020).

As shown in Table 1, the contribution of each economic sector to the Bali GRDP in 1970 was dominated by the primary sector 54.64%, secondary 2.76%, and tertiary 40.60%. The condition of the dominance of the primary sector both to the contribution of GDP and employment, pushed the government at that time to carry out a policy reorientation to encourage increased economic development in the region of Bali and realize the balance of roles between sectors in the Bali region. To realize the new balance of the economic structure of Bali, three sectoral policies were issued namely agricultural development in a broad sense, the development and development of the tourism sector, and the development and development of the small industrial sector (Utama, et al., 2020).

The achievement of minus growth that was almost forgotten was experienced by Bali because it has not happened more than 20 years since the 1998 monetary crisis. Even when Bali was shaken by bombs that shook the world twice, both of them did not make the economic growth of Bali negative. It is not too difficult to predict that the shrinking of the Bali economy this time is mainly due to the outbreak of the disease due to the new Coronavirus (Covid-19) which caused limitation of community movements to prevent or reduce the spread of this pandemic which was felt to be very threatening (Trimurti & Utama, 2021). This paper deals with the recovery strategy for the Bali tourism sector that was already prepared and formulated by the local government as well as the national government level in line with the tourism sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Cultural Attraction

According to Williams and Putra, the tourism promotion strategy usually always connects tradition and culture, further Cuellar argues that there is no tourism without culture, meaning that if an area promotes tourism they promote culture in a destination. Even though in reality business people also offer luxurious facilities, which is interesting to be marketed is the uniqueness of the culture. When linked between the two facts above namely, the Bali Tourism sector has become the leading sector of economic development in the Province of Bali today, this is solely due to the uniqueness of the Balinese Culture itself which has been made an icon by the tourism business of Bali (Lewis, et al., 2013). While Research Suradnya by using the technique of factor analysis has identified eight factors as an attraction for foreign tourists to visit Bali, namely: (1) The prices of tourism products fair, (2) Culture in various manifestations, (3) Beach with all its attractions, (4) Leisure travel, (5) Wide opportunities for relaxation, (6) image of Bali, (7) Natural beauty, (8) Local hospitality. Suradnya research results describe conditions that are somewhat different from the opinion of Williams and Putra, but the factor (ie the 2nd factor) Culture in various forms of manifestation is still a strong enough attraction to attract and encourage foreign tourists to come on holiday to Bali (Pratiwi & Nagari, 2019).

According to Bali Culture Tourism is developed based on local cultural diversity based on Hinduism and is an integral part of national culture, as well as promoting harmony between the goals of tourism development itself so that the goal of preserving Balinese culture that is sustainable can be realized. Whereas Bali Cultural Tourism can be manifested and manifested in the forms

of Historical sites, Balinese architecture, traditions, religious ceremonies, handicrafts, arts and music, local clothing, Balinese local food, and other manifestations inspired by Balinese Hindu culture and religion (Trimurti & Utama, 2020).

Modern Tourism

Modern tourism has now been accelerated by the process of globalization, and also by the rapid development of information technology. The WTO also noted that the internet has become the main media in finding information about tourism destinations that will be visited by potential tourists and an estimated 95% of tourists get information via the internet. Along with that, the growth of internet users continues to grow up to 300% in the next five years along with the rapid advancement of information technology. Another fact is also noted that it is estimated that 80% of tourists visiting destinations in Indonesia come from developed countries who are accustomed to using the internet as a source of information in making tourist travel decisions. However, it must still be realized that the use of information technology advancements in the tourism business is still very limited, only seen in large companies or international networks, even though small industries can utilize information technology at affordable costs, as long as some want to start it (Trimurti & Utama, 2020).

Virtual Technology in tourism is a collaboration between technology and tourism. Virtual can be used in various ways in the tourism industry. This technology is developing very fast and the use of Virtual in tourism is developing along with the technology. Is Virtual tourism the same as games? Virtual works like a normal video that can be viewed on social media or websites, but not like a normal video because users can explore the entire scene while the video is playing. This collaboration requires e-Tourism photography that functions as a tourism video then a free display to pan or swipe the image to see the entire scene required by technology and software applications. Virtual applications in tourism include (1) Virtual reality travel experiences, (2) E-Tourism content for social media or websites, (3) Hotel tours, or destination tours. This virtual travel experience aims to create the same feeling as being in a real destination. The virtual reality travel experience provides users with something truly unique and memorable. The number of travel agents and travel companies that use this technology continues to grow and they promise a bright future in this industry (Untari, 2020).

Implementation of Health Protocol

Another strategy prepared to accelerate the recovery of Bali's tourism is to create and set specific health standards. Specific Health Standards prepared for the tourism industry as stated in Circular Letter Number 3355 of 2020 Concerning the New Era Protocol for the Bali Tourism Sector are as follows: Tourism Destination Managers are required to prepare officers to supervise visitors/tourists, and traders following the New Era of Life Order Protocol. Providing COVID-19 prevention facilities, including: (1) a place to wash hands with their equipment in the area of a tourism destination with the number and distance, (2) adequate and easily accessible; (2) directions for the location of washing hands and hand sanitizers in places that are easily seen; (3) hand sanitizers in the area of tourism destinations at a minimum at the entrance and exit; (4) body temperature gauges (Thermo gun or Thermo scanners) with an amount adjusted to the capacity of visitors/tourists of tourism destinations; and (5) masks for visitors/tourists given free or paid. Checking the body temperature of the visitor/tourist with a Thermo gun or Thermo scanner, and if a body temperature is detected $> 37.30C$ (2 times checking with a distance of 5 minutes), the person concerned is not permitted to enter the tourist destination area and/or coordinate with related parties to get further handling. Provide information media appeal for health protocols. Implementing a queuing system at the entrance or exit and maintaining a minimum distance of 1 meter. Managing distance for managers, visitors, and traders at least 1 meter; (g) conduct a rapid test for managers and traders on independent costs. Prepare non-cash payment facilities and seek ticket sales online; determine operating hours by the policies stipulated by the Regional Government in the provisions of the Legislation. Do disinfect cleaning of places and facilities at the end of every activity in a tourism destination or at least every 4 hours. Obligated to impose sanctions by the provisions in force for visitors, and traders who commit violations, and Facilitate training of employees for the adoption of the New Era of Life Order Protocol (Lumanauw, 2020).

METHOD OF ANALYSIS

This exploration was led in Bali Tourism Destination was structured utilizing a descriptive comparative and confirmatory research study. The research instrument is taken from the government report which deals with health protocol for the tourism sector and then compared with the reality of the Bali Tourism Destination. The indicator used in this study is the application (CHSE) Clean, Health, Safety, and Environment in the industry's accommodation, restaurant, and tourist attraction, and also explains health protocols that

apply to tourism industries in Bali Tourism Destination (Circular Letter Number 3355 of 2020 Concerning The New Era Protocol for The Bali Tourism Sector) (Utama, et al., 2020).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Bali after Covid-19 outbreak

The Bali Tourism destination consist of 8 regencies namely Badung, Gianyar, Bangli, Klungkung, Karangasem, Tabanan, Jembrana, Buleleng, and 1 city that namely Denpasar (see Picture .1)

Picture 1: Map Bali Province (2021) (Lanya, et al., 2018)

In the context of tourism development, linked to the concept of tourism product, a tourist attraction, distance and travel time to the destination is measured from the airport, supporting facilities of tourism, and tourism agencies. When viewed from the number of available accommodations, the Regency of Gianyar, Badung Regency, Denpasar City, Buleleng Regency, and Karangasem Regency are eligible to rely on the sector tourism as a leader of the regional economy (Benur & Bramwell, 2015).

Meanwhile, if seen from the number of 4 and 5-star hotels that already exist in districts and cities in Bali, and if it is assumed that the courage of investors to build star hotels are linked to the popularity of regional tourism, the regency most popular Badung, then followed by Denpasar City, and Gianyar. While the Regencies of Buleleng, Karangasem, and Tabanan may not be as popular as Badung-Denpasar-Gianyar. While the Regencies of Jembrana, Klungkung, and Bangli have not shown as districts that have popularity in the tourism sector (Saputra & Rochis, 2014).

Table 2. Number of Direct Foreign Tourists Arriving in Bali in 2019-2020

Month	Direct Foreign Tourists Arriving in Bali	
	2019	2020
January	455,570	528,883
February	437,456	363,937
March	449,569	156,876
April	477,069	327
May	486,602	36
June	549,516	32
July	604,323	47
August	606,412	22

Month	Direct Foreign Tourists Arriving in Bali	
	2019	2020
September	590,398	83
October	567,967	58
November	498,088	-
December	552,403	-

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics, Province of Bali, 2021

Based on the table above, it can be seen that starting from February 2020 the number of foreign tourists (tourists) began to decline by 31.19% compared to January 2020. Tourism activities in Bali were completely paralyzed in April 2020 with the number of visits by 327 foreign tourists reduced by almost 100% compared to the previous month and year. The situation got worse in the following months with the number of foreign tourists visiting less than 100 per month (Subawa, et al., 2021). With the almost non-existent number of foreign tourist visits to Bali based on the table above, it also directly affects the Room Occupancy Rate of hotels which has decreased drastically as can be seen in Table 3 below.

Table 3. Room Occupancy Rates for Star Hotels in Bali 2019-2020

Month	Room Occupancy Rate (%)	
	2019	2020
January	53.27	59.29
February	56.48	45.98
March	55.43	25.41
April	60.33	3.22
May	51.56	2.07
June	60.37	2,07
July	61,71	2.57
August	67.10	3,68
September	63.22	5.28
October	63.30	9.53
November	59.46	-
December	62.55	-

Source: Central Bureau of Statistics, Province of Bali, 2021

Table 3 shows that the occupancy rate of star-rated hotel rooms began to decline in February 2020, the same month foreign tourist visits to Bali began to decline. As in table 3, the room occupancy rate dropped in April 2020 with a ROR of only 3.22%. It has not experienced any significant changes in the following months. In October 2020, there was an increase in room occupancy by 4.25 points. It has been dominated by domestic tourists, but they were not significantly (Saputra & Rochis, 2014; Bhaskara & Filimonau, 2021).

With more than 500-star hotels in Bali, the room rate of less than 10% since April 2020 has forced the hotel industry to close down. The closure of hotels in Bali due to the pandemic has resulted in hotel workers and employees losing their jobs. As of April 13, 2020, the number of employees laid off was 800 and 46,000 employees, most of whom worked in the hotel and restaurant sector, were sent home (kompas.com, 2020). With the conditions of the Covid-19 pandemic getting worse, an increasing number of employees were dismissed until September 13, 2020, more than 2,500 employees were laid off and more than 73,000 employees were dismissed. The Covid-19 pandemic has not only caused thousands of hotel employees to be laid off but also threatens hotel employees who are still surviving. Hotels are still operating during the pandemic only employ at minimum number, just to maintain the continuity of hotel operations. They are still working not only receive fewer wages compared, and all employees also feel anxious

about situations that are beyond their control and uncertain. The hotel can suddenly decide to send home or even lay off employees due to the unstable economic conditions of the hotel (Cole, et al., 2021).

The worry felt by employees is a sign of Job Insecurity. Job Insecurity is a concept that describes the uncertainty and lack of control over the continuation of employee work in the future. All workers and employees in all industries experience job insecurity because no industry can guarantee a stable job but the feeling of job insecurity is getting worse with the Covid-19 pandemic. Job insecurity can be felt and spreads to all employees due to two specific factors: the first is a change in a company caused by quantitative job insecurity, such as layoffs, downsizing, and mergers that affect employees by triggering feelings of job insecurity, and secondly the emergence of job insecurity. Threats that cause stress that is seen as job insecurity by employees (Karatepe, et al. 2020).

Employees have experienced an increase in job insecurity due to uncertain job status and wage levels, as a result of which there is an increase in turnover intention among employees. With the current unstable condition of Bali tourism without providing a clear view of when Bali tourism can recover, it can be assumed that hotel employees who survive the pandemic experience job insecurity (Hanafiah, et al., 2016).

Recovery of Bali Tourism Destinations with E-Tourism

E-Tourism will help tourism entrepreneurs by application providers E-Tourism through the sale of access services. E-Tourism will have a real impact on the tourism destination in reality because it cannot be provided by E-Tourism service providers, such as humans functioning in their five senses. E-Tourism can only provide impressions because unable to provide taste, smell, emotion, satisfaction, loyalty, and loyalty. The managers of Bali tourism destinations and together with hotel, restaurant, and entertainment establishments, maybe can collaborate each other's utilized by E-Tourism service providers, and also collaborate with all tourism stakeholders by considering collaboration, synergy, and synchronization and harmonization in 4A (Attractions, Access, Amenity, Ancillary) and involving the local community. This strategy is believed to accelerate the recovery of Bali's tourism destinations in the near and long term (Braun & Hollick, 2006).

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Acceleration strategy with Clean, Health, Safety, Environment (CHSE) standards

Another strategy prepared to accelerate the recovery of Bali's tourism is to create and set specific health standards. Specific Health Standards prepared for the tourism industry as stated in Circular Letter Number 3355 of 2020 Concerning the New Era Protocol for the Bali Tourism Sector are as follows:

Table 4. The Indicator of Clean, Health, Safety, Environment (CHSE) standards

Cleanliness	Safety
a) Wash your hands with soap/use a hand sanitizer	a) Procedure for escape from disaster
b) Availability of means of washing hands with soap	b) Availability of first aid kit
c) Cleaning of public spaces and goods utilizing safe and appropriate disinfectants / other cleaning fluids	c) Availability of fire extinguishers
d) Free of vectors and animal disease carriers	d) Availability of assembly points and evacuation routes
e) Cleaning and clean toilet equipment	e) Ensuring electronic devices are turned off when leaving the room
	f) Media and communication mechanisms for handling emergencies

Health	Environment
a) Avoiding physical contact, setting a safe distance, preventing crowds b) Do not touch the face, especially the eyes, nose, mouth c) Check body temperature d) Put on the necessary PPE e) Coughing and sneezing etiquette f) Clean and hygienic food and beverage management g) Simple medical equipment and supplies h) Public spaces and workspaces with good air circulation i) Handling visitors with health problems when on the move at the location.	a) Use of environmentally-friendly equipment and materials b) Use of water and energy sources efficiently and healthily to maintain a balance in the ecosystem c) Waste and liquid waste processing is carried out in a thorough, healthy, and environmentally friendly manner d) The surrounding environment is beautiful and comfortable, either naturally or with technical engineering. e) Monitoring and evaluating the implementation of guidelines and SOPs for the Implementation of Cleanliness, Health, Safety, and Environmental Sustainability

Source: CHSE Guidelines as One of the Government's Efforts to Prevent and Control the Novel Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19) In The Implementation of Indonesia Mice Industry (Subawa, et al., 2021).

At the moment, Bali tourism destinations open their destination only for domestic and local tourists and deal with the implementation of The Indicator of Clean, Health, Safety, Environment (CHSE) standards. All CHSE standards should be implemented that deal with human body contact for all aspects and areas. See Table 5 below

Table 5. Implementation of CHSE Standards

Hotel	Restaurant
a) The entrance to the hotel area b) Lobby (front desk & concierge) c) Guest room d) Restaurant/coffee shop e) Banquet f) Hotel facilities and other public areas g) Kitchen h) Housekeeping i) Office j) Employee room (changing & dining room)	a) Entrance area b) Dining service and drink c) Payment and exit d) Delivery service food and Drink e) Kitchen f) Room administration g) Employee room
Tourist Attraction	Homestay
a) Entrance area b) Counter c) Operation and tourist activities d) Facilities and another public area e) Exit f) Office g) Employee room	a) Reception area b) Bedroom c) Bathroom/ d) toilet e) Kitchen f) Other rooms and areas around the homestay/cottage

Source: CHSE Guidelines as One of the Government's Efforts to Prevent and Control the Novel Corona Virus Disease (Covid-19) In The Implementation of Indonesia Mice Industry (Mahadewi, 2021).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

As straightforward as that e-tourism, they have a significant job as a scaffold between the travel industry makers and likely sightseers. It created in Indonesia as of now has not addressed the most significant part of giving data and sureness to sightseers

when they decide to visit a tourism destination. Most of the providers that build e-tourism systems have the aim of establishing a business partnership or business affiliations with business owners or tourism service providers such as accommodation services, ticketing services, restaurant services, and other services aimed at business. The destinations, hotels, and all related sectors should deal with the implementation of The Indicator of Clean, Health, Safety, Environment (CHSE) standards on their business operations.

Recommendations

So the e-Tourism model as a new Bali normal tourism recovery strategy can be done with a business-to-business (B2B) model between e-Tourism system providers and tourism service providers such as affiliate travel ticket sales, accommodation sales, restaurant services, tourist attraction services in the form of packages virtual tour, as well as direct visitation.

The health protocols should be implemented straight from the Arrival of guests Provision of disinfectant rugs for guest footwear and luggage available at the hotel entrance. Body temperature, health, and travel statements, and guest contact details will be documented. Before entering the hotel area, guests must wear a mask. Guests will be advised to obey the rules of guarding a distance of 1-1.5 meters. The provision of the Perspex screen at the front desk also explains the distance between employees and guests. Services protocol explained health protocols that apply in public places Enforcement of the guard distance of 1 - 1.5 meters. The hotel provides markers on the floor throughout the hotel area to help. Only four people are allowed to enter the elevator at a time. Regular cleaning and disinfection at every point that is often touched by guests in public areas, as well as food and beverage outlets such as door handles or elevator buttons. Non-contact hand sanitizer dispensers are available in crowded areas. The guest capacity in the restaurant, bar, and elevator is reduced.

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